

AIr - Artificial Intelligence Risk of bias tool (AIr)

Appendix 1 - Table of included studies

Number	Title	Lead Author	Reference
1	Improving Fairness in the Prediction of Heart Failure Length of Stay and Mortality by Integrating Social Determinants of Health	Li	(1)
2	Machine Learning From Quantitative Coronary Computed Tomography Angiography Predicts Fractional Flow Reserve-Defined Ischemia and Impaired Myocardial Blood Flow	Lin	(2)
3	Familial Hypercholesterolemia Identification by Machine Learning Using Lipid Profile Data Performs as Well as Clinical Diagnostic Criteria	Hesse	(3)
4	Artificial Intelligence for Contrast-Free MRI: Scar Assessment in Myocardial Infarction Using Deep Learning-Based Virtual Native Enhancement	Zhang	(4)
5	Revealing Unforeseen Diagnostic Image Features With Deep Learning by Detecting Cardiovascular Diseases From Apical 4-Chamber Ultrasounds	Cheng	(5)
6	Artificial Intelligence-Enabled Model for Early Detection of Left Ventricular Hypertrophy and Mortality Prediction in Young to Middle-Aged Adults	Liu	(6)
7	Cardiac Comorbidity Risk Score: Zero-Burden Machine Learning to Improve Prediction of Postoperative Major Adverse Cardiac Events in Hip and Knee Arthroplasty	Onishchenko	(7)
8	rECHOmmend: An ECG-Based Machine Learning Approach for Identifying Patients at Increased Risk of Undiagnosed Structural Heart Disease Detectable by Echocardiography	Ulloa-Cerna	(8)
9	Computational Analysis of Routine Biopsies Improves Diagnosis and Prediction of Cardiac Allograft Vasculopathy	Peyster	(9)
10	GENESIS: Gene-Specific Machine Learning Models for Variants of Uncertain Significance Found in Catecholaminergic Polymorphic Ventricular Tachycardia and Long QT Syndrome-Associated Genes	Draelos	(10)
11	Multiclass Arrhythmia Detection and Classification From Photoplethysmography Signals Using a Deep Convolutional Neural Network	Liu	(11)
12	Predicting Atrial Fibrillation Recurrence by Combining Population Data and Virtual Cohorts of Patient-Specific Left Atrial Models	Roney	(12)
13	Detection of Left Atrial Myopathy Using Artificial Intelligence-Enabled Electrocardiography	Verbrugge	(13)
14	AtheroSpectrum Reveals Novel Macrophage Foam Cell Gene Signatures Associated With Atherosclerotic Cardiovascular Disease Risk	Li	(14)
15	Ultrasonic Texture Features for Assessing Cardiac Remodeling and Dysfunction	Hathaway	(15)
16	Direct Risk Assessment From Myocardial Perfusion Imaging Using Explainable Deep Learning	Singh	(16)
17	Enhanced Diagnosis of Plaque Erosion by Deep Learning in Patients With Acute Coronary Syndromes	Park	(17)
18	Augmented Intelligence to Identify Patients With Advanced Heart Failure in an Integrated Health System	Cheema	(18)
19	Deep Learning Electrocardiographic Analysis for Detection of Left-Sided Valvular Heart Disease	Elias	(19)
20	Artificial Intelligence-Enabled Electrocardiogram Improves the Diagnosis and Prediction of Mortality in Patients With Pulmonary Hypertension	Liu	(20)
21	Prediction of Sudden Cardiac Death Manifesting With Documented Ventricular Fibrillation or Pulseless Ventricular Tachycardia	Chugh	(21)
22	Coronary Risk Estimation Based on Clinical Data in Electronic Health Records	Petrazzini	(22)
23	A Deep Learning Model for Inferring Elevated Pulmonary Capillary Wedge Pressures From the 12-Lead Electrocardiogram	Schlesinger	(23)
24	Solving the Pulmonary Hypertension Paradox in Patients With Severe Tricuspid Regurgitation by Employing Artificial Intelligence	Fortmeier	(24)
25	AI Evaluation of Stenosis on Coronary CTA, Comparison With Quantitative Coronary Angiography and Fractional Flow Reserve: A CREDENCE Trial Substudy	Griffin	(25)
26	Radiomics-Based Precision Phenotyping Identifies Unstable Coronary Plaques From Computed Tomography Angiography	Lin	(26)

27	Understanding and Improving Risk Assessment After Myocardial Infarction Using Automated Left Ventricular Shape Analysis	Acero	(27)
28	Automated Echocardiographic Detection of Severe Coronary Artery Disease Using Artificial Intelligence	Upton	(28)
29	Subclinical Pulmonary Congestion and Abnormal Hemodynamics in Heart Failure With Preserved Ejection Fraction	Jain	(29)
30	Using Deep-Learning Algorithms to Simultaneously Identify Right and Left Ventricular Dysfunction From the Electrocardiogram	Vaid	(30)
31	AI Based CMR Assessment of Biventricular Function: Clinical Significance of Intervendor Variability and Measurement Errors	Wang	(31)
32	Clinical Deployment of Explainable Artificial Intelligence of SPECT for Diagnosis of Coronary Artery Disease	Otaki	(32)

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1. Li Y, Wang H, Luo Y. Improving Fairness in the Prediction of Heart Failure Length of Stay and Mortality by Integrating Social Determinants of Health. *Circulation: Heart Failure*. 2022 Nov;15(11):e009473.
2. Lin A, van Diemen PA, Motwani M, McElhinney P, Otaki Y, Han D, et al. Machine Learning From Quantitative Coronary Computed Tomography Angiography Predicts Fractional Flow Reserve–Defined Ischemia and Impaired Myocardial Blood Flow. *Circulation: Cardiovascular Imaging*. 2022 Oct;15(10):e014369.
3. Hesse R, Raal FJ, Blom DJ, George JA. Familial Hypercholesterolemia Identification by Machine Learning Using Lipid Profile Data Performs as Well as Clinical Diagnostic Criteria. *Circ Genom Precis Med*. 2022 Oct;15(5):e003324.
4. Zhang Q, Burrage MK, Shanmuganathan M, Gonzales RA, Lukaschuk E, Thomas KE, et al. Artificial Intelligence for Contrast-Free MRI: Scar Assessment in Myocardial Infarction Using Deep Learning–Based Virtual Native Enhancement. *Circulation*. 2022 Nov 15;146(20):1492–503.
5. Cheng L, Bosch PBJ, Hofman RFH, Brakenhoff TB, Bruggemans EF, van der Geest RJ, et al. Revealing Unforeseen Diagnostic Image Features With Deep Learning by Detecting Cardiovascular Diseases From Apical 4-Chamber Ultrasounds. *Journal of the American Heart Association*. 2022 Aug 16;11(16):e024168.
6. Liu CM, Hsieh ME, Hu YF, Wei TY, Wu IC, Chen PF, et al. Artificial Intelligence–Enabled Model for Early Detection of Left Ventricular Hypertrophy and Mortality Prediction in Young to Middle-Aged Adults. *Circulation: Cardiovascular Quality and Outcomes*. 2022 Aug;15(8):e008360.
7. Onishchenko D, Rubin DS, van Horne JR, Ward RP, Chattopadhyay I. Cardiac Comorbidity Risk Score: Zero-Burden Machine Learning to Improve Prediction of Postoperative Major Adverse Cardiac Events in Hip and Knee Arthroplasty. *Journal of the American Heart Association*. 2022 Aug 2;11(15):e023745.
8. Ulloa-Cerna AE, Jing L, Pfeifer JM, Raghunath S, Ruhl JA, Rocha DB, et al. rECHOmmend: An ECG-Based Machine Learning Approach for Identifying Patients at Increased Risk of Undiagnosed Structural Heart Disease Detectable by Echocardiography. *Circulation*. 2022 Jul 5;146(1):36–47.
9. Peyster EG, Janowczyk A, Swamidoss A, Kethireddy S, Feldman MD, Margulies KB. Computational Analysis of Routine Biopsies Improves Diagnosis and Prediction of Cardiac Allograft Vasculopathy. *Circulation*. 2022 May 24;145(21):1563–77.
10. Draelos RL, Ezekian JE, Zhuang F, Moya-Mendez ME, Zhang Z, Rosamilia MB, et al. GENESIS: Gene-Specific Machine Learning Models for Variants of Uncertain Significance Found in Catecholaminergic Polymorphic Ventricular Tachycardia and Long QT Syndrome-Associated Genes. *Circulation: Arrhythmia and Electrophysiology*. 2022 Apr;15(4):e010326.
11. Liu Z, Zhou B, Jiang Z, Chen X, Li Y, Tang M, et al. Multiclass Arrhythmia Detection and Classification From Photoplethysmography Signals Using a Deep Convolutional Neural Network. *J Am Heart Assoc*. 2022 Apr 5;11(7):e023555.
12. Roney CH, Sim I, Yu J, Beach M, Mehta A, Alonso Solis-Lemus J, et al. Predicting Atrial Fibrillation Recurrence by Combining Population Data and Virtual Cohorts of Patient-Specific Left Atrial Models. *Circulation: Arrhythmia and Electrophysiology*. 2022 Feb;15(2):e010253.
13. Verbrugge FH, Reddy YNV, Attia ZI, Friedman PA, Noseworthy PA, Lopez-Jimenez F, et al. Detection of Left Atrial Myopathy Using Artificial Intelligence-Enabled Electrocardiography. *Circ Heart Fail*. 2022 Jan;15(1):e008176.
14. Li C, Qu L, Matz AJ, Murphy PA, Liu Y, Manichaikul AW, et al. AtheroSpectrum Reveals Novel Macrophage Foam Cell Gene Signatures Associated With Atherosclerotic Cardiovascular Disease Risk. *Circulation*. 2022 Jan 18;145(3):206–18.
15. Hathaway QA, Yanamala N, Siva NK, Adjeroh DA, Hollander JM, Sengupta PP. Ultrasonic Texture Features for Assessing Cardiac Remodeling and Dysfunction. *J Am Coll Cardiol*. 2022 Dec 6;80(23):2187–201.
16. Singh A, Miller RJH, Otaki Y, Kavanagh P, Hauser MT, Tzolos E, et al. Direct Risk Assessment From Myocardial Perfusion Imaging Using Explainable Deep Learning. *JACC: Cardiovascular Imaging*. 2023 Feb;16(2):209–20.
17. Park S, Araki M, Nakajima A, Lee H, Fuster V, Ye JC, et al. Enhanced Diagnosis of Plaque Erosion by Deep Learning in Patients With Acute Coronary Syndromes. *JACC Cardiovasc Interv*. 2022 Oct 24;15(20):2020–31.
18. Cheema B, Mutharasan RK, Sharma A, Jacobs M, Powers K, Lehrer S, et al. Augmented Intelligence to Identify Patients With Advanced Heart Failure in an Integrated Health System. *JACC: Advances*. 2022 Oct;1(4):100123.
19. Elias P, Poterucha TJ, Rajaram V, Moller LM, Rodriguez V, Bhawe S, et al. Deep Learning Electrocardiographic Analysis for Detection of Left-Sided Valvular Heart Disease. *J Am Coll Cardiol*. 2022 Aug 9;80(6):613–26.
20. Liu CM, Shih ESC, Chen JY, Huang CH, Wu IC, Chen PF, et al. Artificial Intelligence-Enabled Electrocardiogram Improves the Diagnosis and Prediction of Mortality in Patients With Pulmonary Hypertension. *JACC Asia*. 2022 Jun;2(3):258–70.

Appendix 1 – Table of included studies

21. Chugh SS, Reinier K, Uy-Evanado A, Chugh HS, Elashoff D, Young C, et al. Prediction of Sudden Cardiac Death Manifesting With Documented Ventricular Fibrillation or Pulseless Ventricular Tachycardia. *JACC Clin Electrophysiol.* 2022 Apr;8(4):411–23.
22. Petrazzini BO, Chaudhary K, Márquez-Luna C, Forrest IS, Rocheleau G, Cho J, et al. Coronary Risk Estimation Based on Clinical Data in Electronic Health Records. *J Am Coll Cardiol.* 2022 Mar 29;79(12):1155–66.
23. Schlesinger DE, Diamant N, Raghu A, Reinertsen E, Young K, Batra P, et al. A Deep Learning Model for Inferring Elevated Pulmonary Capillary Wedge Pressures From the 12-Lead Electrocardiogram. *JACC: Advances.* 2022 Mar;1(1):100003.
24. Fortmeier V, Lachmann M, Körber MI, Unterhuber M, von Scheidt M, Rippen E, et al. Solving the Pulmonary Hypertension Paradox in Patients With Severe Tricuspid Regurgitation by Employing Artificial Intelligence. *JACC Cardiovasc Interv.* 2022 Feb 28;15(4):381–94.
25. Griffin WF, Choi AD, Riess JS, Marques H, Chang HJ, Choi JH, et al. AI Evaluation of Stenosis on Coronary CTA, Comparison With Quantitative Coronary Angiography and Fractional Flow Reserve: A CRENDENCE Trial Substudy. *JACC Cardiovasc Imaging.* 2023 Feb;16(2):193–205.
26. Lin A, Kolossváry M, Cadet S, McElhinney P, Goeller M, Han D, et al. Radiomics-Based Precision Phenotyping Identifies Unstable Coronary Plaques From Computed Tomography Angiography. *JACC Cardiovasc Imaging.* 2022 May;15(5):859–71.
27. Corral Acero J, Schuster A, Zacur E, Lange T, Stiermaier T, Backhaus SJ, et al. Understanding and Improving Risk Assessment After Myocardial Infarction Using Automated Left Ventricular Shape Analysis. *JACC Cardiovasc Imaging.* 2022 Sep;15(9):1563–74.
28. Upton R, Mumith A, Beqiri A, Parker A, Hawkes W, Gao S, et al. Automated Echocardiographic Detection of Severe Coronary Artery Disease Using Artificial Intelligence. *JACC Cardiovasc Imaging.* 2022 May;15(5):715–27.
29. Jain CC, Tschirren J, Reddy YNV, Melenovsky V, Redfield M, Borlaug BA. Subclinical Pulmonary Congestion and Abnormal Hemodynamics in Heart Failure With Preserved Ejection Fraction. *JACC Cardiovasc Imaging.* 2022 Apr;15(4):629–37.
30. Vaid A, Johnson KW, Badgeley MA, Somani SS, Bicak M, Landi I, et al. Using Deep-Learning Algorithms to Simultaneously Identify Right and Left Ventricular Dysfunction From the Electrocardiogram. *JACC Cardiovasc Imaging.* 2022 Mar;15(3):395–410.
31. Wang S, Patel H, Miller T, Ameyaw K, Narang A, Chauhan D, et al. AI Based CMR Assessment of Biventricular Function: Clinical Significance of Intervendor Variability and Measurement Errors. *JACC Cardiovasc Imaging.* 2022 Mar;15(3):413–27.
32. Otaki Y, Singh A, Kavanagh P, Miller RJH, Parekh T, Tamarappoo BK, et al. Clinical Deployment of Explainable Artificial Intelligence of SPECT for Diagnosis of Coronary Artery Disease. *JACC: Cardiovascular Imaging.* 2022 Jun 1;15(6):1091–102.

Appendix 2

AIr - Tool 1 – for studies that either develop or externally validate an artificial intelligence/machine learning model

Name of the Paper:

Lead Author:

Is this a development or external validation study: Development | External Validation (circle/underline accordingly – if it is both then please use Tool 2)

Domain One: Participants/Data Selection

	Question	Explanation to assist decision	Circle accordingly and justify if needed
Question One	Was data selection defined of an appropriate nature with appropriate inclusions and exclusions?	<p>Appropriate nature data selection would include but not be limited to RCTs, cohort or nested case-control study data. A higher ROB exists when data is extracted from already developed databases rather than longitudinal studies. This higher ROB can be reduced if authors allow for the potential bias in this data set. Furthermore, if the inclusion or exclusion criteria generate a cohort that is not representative of the target population then this increases ROB.</p> <p>Y/PY – both appropriate data selection and inclusions/exclusions. N/PN – If either data selection or inclusion/exclusion criteria are not appropriate. NI – no information .</p>	<p>Yes Probably Yes Probably No No No Information</p> <p>Justification:</p>
Domain One – Risk of Bias			
<p>Low risk of bias if:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Y/PY to appropriate data selection and inclusion/exclusion criteria. - If N/PN relevant to only one aspect of inappropriate data selection of inclusion/exclusion criteria, this could still be a low risk of bias but it should be justified. <p>High risk of bias – if N/PN without justification for a low risk of bias. Unclear – if missing information that could generate a high risk of bias.</p>		<p style="text-align: center;">Low Unclear High</p> <p>Justification:</p>	

Appendix 2

Domain Two: Predictors and Outcomes

	Question	Explanation to assist decision	Circle accordingly and justify if needed
Question Two	Prior to starting analysis, were predictors defined with a method of assessment?	<p>Predictors must be specified with their method of assessment prior to starting to run the analysis so that this doesn't cause biased selection.</p> <p>Y/PY – predictors were defined prior to the analysis commencing. N/PN – predictors were not defined. NI – no information.</p>	<p>Yes Probably Yes Probably No No No Information</p> <p>Justification:</p>
Question Three	Prior to starting analysis, were outcomes and their assessment defined consistently and independent of predictors?	<p>Outcomes can be defined appropriately if they can be objectively measured. If selected after, this increases the risk of bias. If the definition of outcome is based on predictors then this will likely overestimate the correlation between these variables.</p> <p>Y/PY – outcomes defined appropriately and prior to predictors. N/PN – outcomes were not defined prior to predictions or were not appropriate definitions. NI – no information.</p>	<p>Yes Probably Yes Probably No No No Information</p> <p>Justification:</p>
Question Four	At the time point when authors propose that their prediction model is implemented, were appropriate predictors available and was the time period between the information gathered (by predictors) and deciding the outcome achievable?	<p>Are the predictors feasible to ascertain at the point that this prognostic model is intended to be used.</p> <p>Y/PY – at time of intended use, these predictors are available and it would be possible to assess the outcome in line with the paper. N/PN – these predictors are not available at intended time of use. NI – no information.</p>	<p>Yes Probably Yes Probably No No No Information</p> <p>Justification:</p>
Domain Two – Risk of Bias			
<p>Low Risk if – all Y/PY or one N/PN with justification which reduces the bias. Unclear Risk of bias – if there is no information in a question but that is unlikely to affect the results or if there is a N/PN which is partially justified. High risk – if there are questions with multiple NI or the NI would risk altering the bias or if there is N/PN in any question without justification.</p>		<p>Low Unclear High</p> <p>Justification:</p>	

Appendix 2

Domain Three: Analysis

	Question	Explanation to assist decision	Circle accordingly and justify if needed
Question Five	Was the outcome represented adequately in the participant selection?	<p>The outcome needs to be represented enough in the sample to ensure that the result is valid without a risk of insufficient power to achieve a significant result or overestimation.</p> <p>Y/PY For model development studies, events per variable (EPV) should be over 20. An EPV between 10-20 could be considered although there is limited evidence for this. For model validation studies, participants with the outcome should be over 100.</p> <p>N/PN – EPV under 10 or participants with outcome is under 100 respectively. NI – no information.</p>	<p>Yes Probably Yes Probably No No No Information</p> <p>Justification:</p>
Question Six	Were valid methods used for identification of the outcome which would correctly classify the condition without oversimplification	<p>Valid methods would include continuous predictors that remained as continuous variables without categorisation and categorical predictor groups were sorted according to a pre-defined group.</p> <p>Y/PY – continuous predictors remained as continuous variables without categorisation and if categorical predictor groups are using a pre-defined group. N/PN – no specified categorical groups. Continuous variables dichotomised. NI – no information.</p>	<p>Yes Probably Yes Probably No No No Information</p> <p>Justification:</p>
Question Seven	Were all participants included in the analysis including how missing data was handled and information for those who dropped out?	<p>There is a risk of bias associated with missing data due to the possibility of the missing data being correlated with an outcome.</p> <p>Y/PY – All participants are enrolled. No participants were removed from analysis due to missing data. If they were then there is an adequate explanation and this is a small number that would be unlikely to alter the outcome of the analysis. N/PN – participants were removed from analysis due to missing data without explanation/justification. If a subgroup were excluded from analysis. NI – no information.</p>	<p>Yes Probably Yes Probably No No No Information</p> <p>Justification:</p>
Question Eight	Were both confounding factors and other complexities accounted for in the analysis	<p>Examples of complexities in the analysis would include censoring, completing risks and sampling of control participants etc.</p> <p>Y/PY – Complexities and confounding have been accounted for. N/PN – Not been accounted for. NI – no information.</p>	<p>Yes Probably Yes Probably No No No Information</p> <p>Justification:</p>
Question Nine	Has model calibration and discrimination been assessed (<i>with</i>	<p>Both calibration and discrimination are assessed with a calibration plot, an adequate size of the data and are assessed by suitable statistical tests.</p>	<p>Yes Probably Yes Probably No No No Information</p>

Appendix 2

	<i>consideration for overfitting – in model development studies)?</i>	In model development studies, there should be assessment of internal validation to mitigate overfitting. Overfitting of a model suggests that predictions might not be applicable to new studies. To mitigate this, internal validation must be assessed, eg through cross-validation or bootstrapping Y/PY – calibration and discrimination have been assessed with consideration with an interval validation assessment in model development studies. N/PN – this has not been considered. NI – no information.	Justification:
Question 10 - For Model Development Studies only			
Question Ten	Was the final model produced clearly linked to a singular multivariable analysis which in turn is independent of univariable analyses?	There is an increased risk of bias if multiple univariable analyses are computed prior to grouping the statistically significant variables together and forming a multivariable analysis. Y/PY – if predictors were not based on univariable analysis. The final model directly links to the multivariable analysis. N/PN – if predictors are based on univariable analysis prior to multivariable modelling. NI – no information.	Yes Probably Yes Probably No No No Information Justification:
Domain Three – Risk of Bias			
<p>Low Risk if: All Y/PY or if there is no information in a question but that is unlikely to affect the results or if there is a N/PN which is justified.</p> <p>Unclear Risk of bias – missing information which is unlikely to affect results but we cannot be sure.</p> <p>High risk - if there are questions with multiple NI or the NI would risk altering the bias or if there is Y/PY in any question without justification.</p>		<p style="text-align: center;">Low Unclear High</p> <p>Justification:</p>	

Overall Outcome:

Overall – Risk of Bias	
<p>Low Risk if: Low in all domains, or unclear in one as long as justified.</p> <p>Unclear Risk of bias – unclear in one domain but not justified or a high risk justified.</p> <p>High risk: Any high risks not justified or multiple unclear risks.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Low Unclear High</p> <p>Justification:</p>

Appendix 3

Air - Tool 2 – for studies that develop AND externally validate an artificial intelligence/machine-learned model

Name of the Paper:

Lead Author:

This should be both a development and external validation study. Domain One and Domain Three will be repeated twice for development and validation. If the study is only analysing one then please use Tool 1.

Domain One: Participants/Data Selection

	Question	Explanation to assist decision	Circle accordingly and justify if needed
Development	Question One	<p>Was data selection defined of an appropriate nature with appropriate inclusions and exclusions?</p> <p>Appropriate nature data selection would include but not be limited to RCTs, cohort or nested case-control study data. A higher ROB exists when data is extracted from already developed databases rather than longitudinal studies. This higher ROB can be reduced if authors allow for the potential bias in this data set. Furthermore, if the inclusion or exclusion criteria generate a cohort that is not representative of the target population then this increases ROB.</p> <p>Y/PY – both appropriate data selection and inclusions/exclusions. N/PN – If either data selection or inclusion/exclusion criteria are not appropriate. NI – no information.</p>	<p>Yes Probably Yes Probably No No No Information</p> <p>Justification:</p>
	Domain One – Risk of Bias		
	<p>Low risk of bias if:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Y/PY to appropriate data selection and inclusion/exclusion criteria. - If N/PN relevant to only one aspect of inappropriate data selection of inclusion/exclusion criteria, this could still be a low risk of bias but it should be justified. <p>High risk of bias – if N/PN without justification for a low risk of bias. Unclear – if missing information that could generate a high risk of bias.</p>	<p>Low Unclear High</p> <p>Justification:</p>	

	Question	Explanation to assist decision	Circle accordingly and justify if needed
External Validation	Question One	<p>Was data selection defined of an appropriate nature with appropriate inclusions and exclusions?</p> <p>Appropriate nature data selection would include but not be limited to RCTs, cohort or nested case-control study data. A higher ROB exists when data is extracted from already developed databases rather than longitudinal studies. This higher ROB can be reduced if authors allow for the potential bias in this data set. Furthermore, if the inclusion or exclusion criteria generate a cohort that is not representative of the target population then this increases ROB.</p> <p>Y/PY – both appropriate data selection and inclusions/exclusions. N/PN – If either data selection or inclusion/exclusion criteria are not appropriate. NI – no information.</p>	<p>Yes Probably Yes Probably No No No Information</p> <p>Justification:</p>

Appendix 3

<i>Domain One – Risk of Bias</i>	
<p>Low risk of bias if:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Y/PY to appropriate data selection and inclusion/exclusion criteria. - If N/PN relevant to only one aspect of inappropriate data selection of inclusion/exclusion criteria, this could still be a low risk of bias but it should be justified. <p>High risk of bias – if N/PN without justification for a low risk of bias. Unclear – if missing information that could generate a high risk of bias.</p>	<p>Low Unclear High</p> <p>Justification:</p>

Domain Two: Predictors and Outcomes (For both development and external validation – only complete once)

	Question	Explanation to assist decision	Circle accordingly and justify if needed
Question Two	Prior to starting analysis, were predictors defined with a method of assessment?	<p>Predictors must be specified with their method of assessment prior to starting to run the analysis so that this doesn't cause biased selection.</p> <p>Y/PY – predictors were defined prior to the analysis commencing. N/PN – predictors were not defined. NI – no information.</p>	<p>Yes Probably Yes Probably No No No Information</p> <p>Justification:</p>
Question Three	Prior to starting analysis, were outcomes and their assessment defined consistently and independent of predictors?	<p>Outcomes can be defined appropriately if they can be objectively measured. If selected after, this increases the risk of bias. If the definition of outcome is based on predictors then this will likely overestimate the correlation between these variables.</p> <p>Y/PY – outcomes defined appropriately and prior to predictors. N/PN – outcomes were not defined prior to predictions or were not appropriate definitions. NI – no information.</p>	<p>Yes Probably Yes Probably No No No Information</p> <p>Justification:</p>
Question Four	At the time point when authors propose that their prediction model is implemented, were appropriate predictors available and was the time period between the information gathered (by predictors) and deciding the outcome achievable?	<p>Are the predictors feasible to ascertain at the point that this prognostic model is intended to be used.</p> <p>Y/PY – at time of intended use, these predictors are available and it would be possible to assess the outcome in line with the paper. N/PN – these predictors are not available at intended time of use. NI – no information.</p>	<p>Yes Probably Yes Probably No No No Information</p> <p>Justification:</p>
<i>Domain Two – Risk of Bias</i>			
<p>Low Risk if – all Y/PY or one N/PN with justification which reduces the bias. Unclear Risk of bias – if there is no information in a question but that is unlikely to affect the results or if there is a N/PN which is partially justified. High risk – if there are questions with multiple NI or the NI would risk altering the bias or if there is N/PN in any question without justification.</p>			<p>Low Unclear High</p> <p>Justification:</p>

Appendix 3

Domain Three: Analysis – Development and External Validation separately

	Question	Explanation to assist decision	Circle accordingly and justify if needed
Development	Question Five Was the outcome represented adequately in the participant selection?	The outcome needs to be represented enough in the sample to ensure that the result is valid without a risk of insufficient power to achieve a significant result or overestimation. Y/PY - For model development studies, events per variable (EPV) should be over 20. An EPV between 10-20 could be considered although there is limited evidence for this. N/PN – EPV under 10. NI – no information.	Yes Probably Yes Probably No No No Information Justification:
	Question Six Were valid methods used for identification of the outcome which would correctly classify the condition without oversimplification	Valid methods would include continuous predictors that remained as continuous variables without categorisation and categorical predictor groups were sorted according to a pre-defined group. Y/PY – continuous predictors remained as continuous variables without categorisation and if categorical predictor groups are using a pre-defined group. N/PN – no specified categorical groups. Continuous variables dichotomised. NI – no information.	Yes Probably Yes Probably No No No Information Justification:
	Question Seven Were all participants included in the analysis including how missing data was handled and information for those who dropped out?	There is a risk of bias associated with missing data due to the possibility of the missing data being correlated with an outcome. Y/PY – All participants are enrolled. No participants were removed from analysis due to missing data. If they were then there is an adequate explanation and this is a small number that would be unlikely to alter the outcome of the analysis. N/PN – participants were removed from analysis due to missing data without explanation/justification. If a subgroup were excluded from analysis. NI – no information.	Yes Probably Yes Probably No No No Information Justification:
	Question Eight Were both confounding factors and other complexities accounted for in the analysis	Examples of complexities in the analysis would include censoring, completing risks and sampling of control participants etc. Y/PY – Complexities and confounding have been accounted for. N/PN – Not been accounted for. NI – no information.	Yes Probably Yes Probably No No No Information Justification:
	Question Nine Has model calibration and discrimination been assessed with consideration for overfitting – in model development studies?	Both calibration and discrimination are assessed with a calibration plot, an adequate size of the data and are assessed by suitable statistical tests. In model development studies, there should be assessment of internal validation to mitigate overfitting. Overfitting of a model suggests that predictions might not be applicable to new studies. To mitigate this, internal validation must be assessed, eg through cross-validation or bootstrapping Y/PY – calibration and discrimination have been assessed with consideration with an interval validation assessment.	Yes Probably Yes Probably No No No Information Justification:

Appendix 3

		N/PN – this has not been considered. NI – no information.	
Question 10 - For Model Development Studies only			
Question Ten	Was the final model produced clearly linked to a singular multivariable analysis which in turn is independent of univariable analyses?	There is an increased risk of bias if multiple univariable analyses are computed prior to grouping the statistically significant variables together and forming a multivariable analysis. Y/PY – if predictors were not based on univariable analysis. The final model directly links to the multivariable analysis. N/PN – if predictors are based on univariable analysis prior to multivariable modelling. NI – no information.	Yes Probably Yes Probably No No No Information Justification:
Domain Three – Risk of Bias			
Low Risk if: All Y/PY or if there is no information in a question but that is unlikely to affect the results or if there is a N/PN which is justified. Unclear Risk of bias – missing information which is unlikely to affect results but we cannot be sure. High risk - if there are questions with multiple NI or the NI would risk altering the bias or if there is Y/PY in any question without justification.			Low Unclear High Justification:

External Validation		Question	Explanation to assist decision	Circle accordingly and justify if needed
	Question Five	Was the outcome represented adequately in the participant selection?	The outcome needs to be represented enough in the sample to ensure that the result is valid without a risk of insufficient power to achieve a significant result or overestimation. Y/PY - For model validation studies, participants with the outcome should be over 100. N/PN – participants with outcome is under 100 respectively. NI – no information.	Yes Probably Yes Probably No No No Information Justification:
	Question Six	Were valid methods used for identification of the outcome which would correctly classify the condition without oversimplification	Valid methods would include continuous predictors that remained as continuous variables without categorisation and categorical predictor groups were sorted according to a pre-defined group. Y/PY – continuous predictors remained as continuous variables without categorisation and if categorical predictor groups are using a pre-defined group. N/PN – no specified categorical groups. Continuous variables dichotomised. NI – no information.	Yes Probably Yes Probably No No No Information Justification:
	Question Seven	Were all participants included in the analysis including how missing	There is a risk of bias associated with missing data due to the possibility of the missing data being correlated with an outcome.	Yes Probably Yes Probably No No No Information

Appendix 3

	data was handled and information for those who dropped out?	Y/PY – All participants are enrolled. No participants were removed from analysis due to missing data. If they were then there is an adequate explanation and this is a small number that would be unlikely to alter the outcome of the analysis. N/PN – participants were removed from analysis due to missing data without explanation/justification. If a subgroup were excluded from analysis. NI – no information.	Justification:
Question Eight	Were both confounding factors and other complexities accounted for in the analysis	Examples of complexities in the analysis would include censoring, completing risks and sampling of control participants etc. Y/PY – Complexities and confounding have been accounted for. N/PN – Not been accounted for. NI – no information.	Yes Probably Yes Probably No No No Information Justification:
Question Nine	Has model calibration and discrimination been assessed?	Both calibration and discrimination are assessed with a calibration plot, an adequate size of the data and are assessed by suitable statistical tests. Y/PY – calibration and discrimination have been assessed. N/PN – this has not been considered. NI – no information.	Yes Probably Yes Probably No No No Information Justification:
Domain Three – Risk of Bias			
Low Risk if: All Y/PY or if there is no information in a question but that is unlikely to affect the results or if there is a N/PN which is justified. Unclear Risk of bias – missing information which is unlikely to affect results but we cannot be sure. High risk - if there are questions with multiple NI or the NI would risk altering the bias or if there is Y/PY in any question without justification.			Low Unclear High Justification:

Overall Risk of Bias for Development and External Validation
Circle as appropriate

